

INDIFFERENCE AS A PHILOSOPHICAL CATEGORY: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS

Kendjaev Ulugbek Muratovich

Researcher at Navoi State Pedagogical Institute
Navoi, Uzbekistan

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Annotation: In the realm of philosophical perspectives, the concept of indifference signifies an individual's disinterest in societal processes, specific activities, and a negligent stance towards the environment. This article delves into the emotional, epistemological, axiological, and praxeological dimensions of indifference, drawing upon the viewpoints of philosophers like Thomas More, Francis Bacon, Thomas Hobbes, John Locke, Francois Voltaire, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, Paul Holbach, Akhmad Donish, Sattorkhan Abdulgafarov, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, and Abdullah Avloni. Through the exploration of these philosophical standpoints, the article scrutinizes the various interpretations and adverse implications associated with indifference.

Key words: indifference, theology, philosophy, society, nirvana, meditation, enlightenment, spirituality, maturity, virtue, freedom, purity, utopia.

As human society is constantly developing, it is known to all of us that this process becomes intensive in the era of globalization. As a result, social activity is increasing in a certain group of society members, while in another group, indifference to social processes and events is forming. The alarming aspect is that the number of people who are indifferent to the events happening in the world, especially in Uzbekistan, and are indifferent to reforms is increasing more and more. In some cases, indifference prevents the deep rooting of various social problems and the successful implementation of large-scale social reforms.

Man is, first of all, a social being. Therefore, his happiness, prosperous and peaceful life is directly connected with social conditions. In some philosophical teachings, abstaining from participation in the events and processes taking place in the external world, being indifferent to them is defined as a sign of intelligence. For instance, in the teaching of Buddhism, which arose in Ancient India in the 6th century BC and later spread throughout Asia, the highest goal of a person is connected with reaching the state of nirvana. Nirvana is a state of mind free from all desires. Such a state can be achieved by detaching from the external world, becoming indifferent to it, and instead indulging in meditation [1]. Plato, a bright representative of ancient world philosophy, also mentions indifference to social processes as a symbol of rationality. In his opinion, only indifference insures a person against excessive passion and worries. These

views of the great thinker were further developed by the schools of Cynics and Stoics. In medieval Christian ethics, cases of indifference being described in a neutral sense can be seen in the teachings of representatives of Christian ascetics. The Christian theologian Evagrius of Pontus in his treatise “Speech on Spiritual Practices or the Monk” calls indifference the supreme ideal of a true monk [2]. According to Aurelius Augustine, indifference means freedom from various passions. But since people are not freed from all their passions and feelings, they cannot be detached from worldly concerns and cannot be completely indifferent to them [3].

According to Muslim philosophers in medieval Eastern philosophy, any indifference is not a virtue. True, indifference to worldly affairs, transient passions, and material goods, that is, the ability to control the ego, is a sign of intelligence. Because, according to the confession of Sufis, “the inability to control the ego, the desire to accumulate wealth, that is, the continuous desire to accumulate wealth, honors the human body with fleeting pleasures. A person caught on the hook of such pleasure and pleasure begins to rage like wild animals, his anger increases. The combination of lust and anger in a person further develops animal behavior and destroys compassionate qualities. As a result, such people begin to become spiritually impoverished. Therefore, according to the Sufis, it is necessary for a person not to give free rein to his ego, but to be able to control it at the right time. Not giving free rein to the ego, being able to control it is the guarantee of spiritual maturity” [4]. However, according to mystics, indifference to public interests and people’s concerns is not considered a virtue.

The way of life established during the Renaissance completely changed the paradigm of relations between man and society. An active person has stopped indifference to social affairs and social processes. In line with this, the anthropocentric philosophy of the Renaissance began to interpret social activity and work as a source of encouragement for human purity. In his work entitled “Utopia”, Thomas More emphasized the need for every person to actively participate in the affairs of society, and his value is determined by his good work and social activities [5].

European philosophers F. Bacon, T. Hobbes, J. Locke, French enlighteners F. Voltaire, E. de Condillac, J. J. Rousseau, and P. Holbach expressed different opinions about people in the 17th and 18th centuries. In their opinion, they explained the need to see a person not as a person who lives independently of

others and is indifferent to social processes, but as a breed that actively participates in the affairs of society and ensures its well-being [6].

In the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, Central Asian enlighteners Ahmad Donish, Sattarkhan Abdulhafarov, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abdulla Avloni wrote about the development of society depending on the activity of its members. In addition, it is possible to find comments that the spiritual maturity of a person is determined by his serving the general interests of society, and that indifference to social processes causes the decline of both society and the individual.

Such considerations, developed in the philosophical thinking of the new era, created a theoretical basis for characterizing indifference as a social evil, not a sign of intelligence. Indifference to these theoretical foundations began to be described as a serious social, political, existential and psychological problem, not a sign of sanity and tranquility [7]. X. Ortega-i-Gasset, G. Blumer and J. Baudryyar called indifference one of the indispensable and important attributes of mass society [8]. According to them, the change in the content and direction of socio-economic, political and cultural processes in society made a person indifferent to social processes [9].

Ch. R. Mills and P. Bourdieu focus on the political processes in mass society that caused the indifference of the individual [10]. However, personal indifference is not the result of political processes. According to G. Marcuse, it is also a product of the economic arbitrariness and consumer frenzy settled in the mass society [11].

By the 21st century, personal apathy has become one of the most significant social problems. Therefore, scientific efforts to study its nature, to determine its causes and consequences, and to search for ways to eliminate it became active. In Uzbekistan, various mass media and electronic publications repeatedly talk and write about the fact that indifference has become one of the serious social problems. There are also attempts to reveal its nature in the context of various scientific problems. The opinions of thinkers and experts on the topic serve as a theoretical-methodological basis for defining the content and components of the concept of "indifference", for describing in detail the social and personal factors that cause it, and for predicting its social consequences.

References:

1. Филимонов А.А., Бетехтина Е. Н., Кузнецова А. В., Трапезников М.В. Специфика буддизма как философии и религии. //Colloquium-journal, 2019, №1. - 55-58-с.

2. Евагрий Понтийский. Слово о духовном делании, или Монах.// Творения аввы Евагрия: Аскетические и богословные трактаты.- М.: Мартис, 1994.- С.94-112.
3. Столяров А. Апатия.// Философская антропология, 2023, Т.9, №1.- 186-с.
4. Чориев А. Инсон фалсафаси. Инсон тўғрисидаги фалсафий фикрлар тараққиёти. Биринчи китоб.- Т.: Ўзб.файл. миллий жам. нашр., 2007.- Б.212.
5. Мор Т. Утопия.- М.: Наука, 1978. -с.417
6. Чориев А. Инсон фалсафаси. Инсон тўғрисидаги фалсафий фикрлар тараққиёти. - Т.: Ўзб.файл. миллий жам. нашр., 2007. -Б.289-305.
7. Набок Ю.В. Феномен социальной апатии в современном обществе: Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филос.н.- Самара: Самарский филиал МГПУ, 2005. - с.5.
8. Бодрийяр Ж. В тени молчаливого большинства, или конец социального. -Екатеринбург: Изд-во Уральского университета, 2000. Блумер, Г. Коллективное поведение. // Американская социологическая мысль.- М.: Изд-во МГУ, 1994.- С. 90-115.
9. Ортега-и-Гассет Х. Восстание масс.// Избранные труды.- М.: Весь мир, 1997. – 704 с.
10. Mills, C. W. White Collar: The American Middle Classes (50th anniversary ed.). -New York: Oxford University Press, 2002; Бурдьё П. Начала.- М.: Socio-Logos, 1994. -288 с.
11. Маркузе Г. Одномерный человек. — М.: “Refl-book”, 1994. - 368 с.
12. Турдиев, Б. (2024). JAMIYAT IDEOSFERASINING IJTIMOIIY-FALSAFIY TAHLILI. Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences., 4(2).
13. Турдиев, Б. (2023). IBN SINONING HUQUQIY TA'LIMOTLAR RIVOJIDA QO 'SHGAN HISSASI. Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences., 3(S/3), 214-220.
14. Turdiyev, B. S. (2023). KONFUTSIYNING SIYOSIY- HUQUQIY TA'LIMOT RIVOJIGA QO 'SHGAN HISSASI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3(21), 519-522.
15. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). Manifestations of Moral Threats in the Ideosphere of Uzbekistan and Their Prevention Strategy. Asian Journal of Basic Science & Research, 5(1), 103-108.